

Uḍḍīśatantra

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Sanskrit literature, Magic, Tantra, Tantra, Tantra, Hindu Tantra, Śaivism, Tantra, Hinduism

A widely published Sanskrit tantra on magic. It can be grouped in the Uḍḍ corpus, a hybrid group of magical texts sharing the Uḍḍ-prefix in their titles, such as the Uḍḍāmeśvaratantra or Uḍḍāmaratantra. Its title means the tantra of the leaping or bellowing lord. Topics include sorcery, fantastic feats, enchanted objects, and conjuring, mostly of female creatures. The ṣaṭkarmani include the following: 1. śānti-puṣṭi (tranquilizing-increase) 2. vaśīkaraṇa (subjugating) 3. stambhana (immobilizing) 4. mohana (bewildering) 5. vidveṣana (dissent) 6. uccāṭana (eradicating) 7. ākarṣaṇa (attracting) 8. mārana (murder) These are the main rituals in the Uḍḍīśatantra. They are expanded in detail for the majority of the text, but the source also contains "meta-data" that explain the reasons for variations in ritual actions and ingredients. The metadata also nuances the results. Such magic rituals reveal the social worlds and material cultures of the authors. The text closes with sections describing general rituals and enchanted objects that are not easily classified under the rubric of the six results. Of note is that this text is spoke by Śiva to Rāvaṇa, the demon king of Lanka, famous adversary in the Rāmāyana. The text is difficult to date, as are most of the tantras in the genre of magic ritual tantras. There are many scattered manuscripts, but my instinct is that it is 1400s at the absolute earliest. New versions continue to be published. The most recent version I have consulted is published in 2009.

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2009 CE

Region: South Asia

Region tags: Asia, South Asia

South Asia

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Mishra Giri Ratna. *Laṅkeśa Rāvaṇa's Uḍḍīśa Tantra = Uḍḍīśatantra : With Sarveshwari English Commentary & Introduction*. First ed. Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan 2015.
- Source 2: Tripathi, Syamsundarlal, "Lakṣmīveṅkaṭeśvara" *Śṭīm-Presa*, Kalyāṇa-Baṃbaī, 1938 Show more information

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4vt6f325>

– Source 1 Description: <https://scroll.in/magazine/975003/how-to-destroy-enemies-and-walk-on-water-according-to-old-indian-magic-texts>

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2077-1444/8/9/188>

Notes: Scans are beginning to be available for older versions. There are some passages translated. I most often see passages on web sites for sorcerers selling their services.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/uddish-tantra-pt-shyam-sundar-lal-tripathi-muradabadi/page/n35/mode/2up>

– Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/uddisa-tantra-sinhala-ceylon-ravana-books-archives>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

Number of sheets

– Multiple sheets

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Plant leaves

Species

– Specify: Palm

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Ritual preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Ritual preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– I don't know

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

– I don't know

Notes: The text is written in a sort of low sanskrit. The text is published in a wide variety of

vernacular languages, sometimes with the sanskrit also printed.

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 1000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– I don't know

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– I don't know

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– Yes

Notes: It seems that a wider knowledge of magic including scholarship informs current sorcerers.

↳ How might emic and scholarly (anthropological) assessments of the audience differ?

– Specify: Some would scholars would see them as sorcerers, some practicing would see them as heroes.

↳ How might emic and scholarly (anthropological) assessments of the audience be similar?

– Specify: Some epic understandings map well, especially the tantra sorcerer as a, well, sorcerer.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The reader will be an able to perform rituals that can affect the world. The master of such rituals is thought to have limitless power.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– No

Notes: Reciting the text would have no effect per se, but the reciting of mantras and spells would inherently have effect as they are words of power.

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: Magic Rituals

Notes: Rituals of sorcery are called the six results, including murder, pacification, increased, eradication, mutiny, attraction, bewildering and so forth. There are also fantastic feats and enchanted objects that enable the sorcerer to roam the sky or use magic lamps to find treasures. Goddess and female sprit beings are conjured forth to confer all many of wealth and divine substances and powers.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 1

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: Ad hoc

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– I don't know

Notes: Theoretically a guru could check that the ritual is done correctly. However, if the rite is done incorrectly then there would be no effects.

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Yes

- ↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
 - Yes

Is there material significance to the text?

- No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

- Yes

- ↳ Calligraphy?

- Yes

Notes: Special forms of writing mantras, especially in mystical diagrams.

- ↳ Illustrations?

- Yes

Notes: Handwritten manuscripts, in particular will have magic diagrams fully written out based on the text. These could be used in rituals or reproduced on amulets.

- ↳ Illuminations?

- No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

- Yes

- ↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

- Yes

- ↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

- Yes

Notes: Clearer and longer versions are considered better. the wider the range of content the better they are. If a text is devoted to a specific deity that the reader propitiates then it would be better.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

Notes: A text is more authoritative by being more complete....sometimes older texts are more authoritative, but the readers seem to value the most extensive versions. All versions are revealed by Shiva or Bhairava.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text belongs to a genre. Some collections of Uḍḍīśas are found under larger sources called Rāvanasaṃhitā, the scriptures of Rāvaṇa, yet that Rāvaṇa, demon king of Lanka.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Luni-solar? (Combined, as in Mayan, Javanese, or Cham calendars)

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– Yes

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– Yes

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– Yes

↳ Divorce?

– Yes

↳ Warfare?

– Yes

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

↳ Trade/commerce?

– Yes

↳ Festivals?

– No

↳ Pilgrimages?

– No

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: The body and the spirit are connected with the actions of the body effecting the sprit. However, I see no evidence of explicit soul flight or the like.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Heaven is the ultimate aspiration, to be reborn in heaven or as a godly creature is an aspiration as well.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– I don't know

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife state is finite.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Notes: There is a sorta vague status quo with nobody really speculating too hard.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form?

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: In Hinduism the goal is being merged into the realm of the ancestors, but there may be incarnation after that.

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– I don't know

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Notes: Not in this text but in other Hindu texts that are the background for this text.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

Notes: The grave goods are used in other rituals.

↳ Personal effects?

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– Yes

↳ Significant value? (Gold, jade, so forth)

– Yes

↳ Some value? (valuable, or useful objects)

– No

↳ Other grave goods?

– I don't know

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Cremation grounds and, rarely, graves are locations to perform magic rituals. Also, substances such as bones, shrouds, and ash are gathered from cremation grounds and used in rituals.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Shiva and the Goddess or Bhairava are seen as having full dominion over these rituals.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic

terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

|

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes

- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes

- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - Yes

- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No

- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No

- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes

 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes

 - ↳ In trance possession
 - Yes

 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - Yes

 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

Notes: It seems so, but it is vague. There is always the possibility of revelation.

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– Yes

Notes: There are some rituals that prepare the yogi for a vision.

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits or ghosts can be called forth to cause disease or death.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: They are seen in that they are visualized with appearance, and tantric yogis would describe this as a sense experience. They are not necessarily corporeal.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In other contexts the beings are felt, but I do not see evidence of physical sensation in anything but conjuring, in which one feels a breeze or hears the tinkling of jewelry

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: This is a tricky one because the beings are so varied. Some have specific personalities and others are general, sorta like representatives of a group of demons like fever demons, obstructors and the like. They seem to know everything but they rarely confer knowledge directly.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: The wide range of supernatural beings from gods to demon gods to demons have direct effect on life. Many of these rituals manipulate such beings to get the required aims, positive for oneself, negative and even lethal for others.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: This is a hard one. They are thought to communicate, but they do so in all sorts of manners, or they are said to communicate but the manner is not described.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Happy beings, happy life.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: Negative beings will harm individuals and disrupt life.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: They hunger for offerings, and when they are satisfied they will do the will of the sorcerer.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

Notes: Clans of deities and demigods

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Notes: A flow chart of deities starting with Siva or Bhairava down to the lowliest ghost or demon or disease.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Some deities are located in a domain, some are called to a space and then they have domain. Sometimes specific to disease or affliction. Some to emotions, like Kamadeva and love.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Paranormal?

Notes: Multiple non physical beings may appear or be manipulated. Preta, Bhūta, Yakṣiṇī, Yoginī, and the like.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– No

↳ Divination through human communication?

– Yes

↳ Human being the vehicle for the oracle?

– Yes

Notes: Some discussion of possession of children who are like oracles.

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified class?

– No

↳ Is sex-deprivation required?

– No

↳ Are intoxicants required?

– Yes

Notes: Intoxicants are required in many rites.

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material?

– Smoke

Notes: All of the above. Bones are examined to some degree but most divination has to do with signs on the body, for instance the manner in which a fetus resides in a woman. Appearance of flame types. Also there is smearing the hands or swords with oil and looking for patterns.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but the supernatural sees antisocial behaviors as powerful.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Notes: The rituals feed and placate gods and spirits to get them to do the will of the yogi.

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?
– Yes
Notes: Very Rarely

↳ Sacred objects?
– Yes

↳ Daily life objects?
– Yes

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– Yes
Notes: Some very much care about taboos, some glory in violating them.

↳ Food
– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)
– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– No
Notes: I mean, all these rituals are used to attack others, usually disliked others but also intimate others.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– Yes

↳ Adultery

– No

↳ Incest

– No

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: They endorse sorcery

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Notes: Any failure in ritual will lead to the ritual not working or the deities conferring ill effects.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: They are almost totally oriented toward ritual.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Notes: If they have a sacred space or temple, that must be maintained. That said, they are often invoked in ruined temples.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: All the ills of the world MAY be caused by gods or may be caused by demons.

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– No

Notes: There are ways to learn, but the gods are capricious.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

- ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - Yes
- ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - Yes
- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - Yes
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Notes: All rewards, supernatural and otherwise, are conferred mechanically by rituals or they are given by supernatural entities who are affected by these rituals.

- ↳ Done only by high god
 - No
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– No

↳ Done randomly
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
– Yes

Notes: Most results are this worldly but there are some otherworldly. The text exists in the general overlap with metaphysics of Hinduism.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– Yes

Notes: Evidence of all these rewards based on the successful performance of rituals. These rituals are pragmatic, shaping the life of the practitioner based on their desires for performing such rituals.

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

Notes: Some rites are scattered throughout that may confer liberation (mokṣa) but they are advanced along side other rites for murder, so it may be a euphemism. That said, conjuring a female spirit being may cause the sorcerer to ride upon her back into the heavens.

- ↳ At specified time in future

– No

- ↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

- ↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: When rites are successful.

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

- ↳ Divine judgment event

– No

- ↳ Restoration of the world

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– I don't know

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: I would argue that tantra in general ascribes to social norms when not in the ritual arena.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: In these magic tantras it seems that everything is conventional. While the usual conventions apply, in these rituals conventions are violated to create powerful rites.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The issues of morality are vague. The text advocates selfishness and greed in service of success in the world.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Depends on the particular ritual, some require fasting, others feasting.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: Specific rituals will require abstaining from certain foods and types of foods.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– Yes

Notes: A few powerful rituals imply and sometimes state the offering of human life and flesh.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– Yes

Notes: A few rituals do require human life and flesh offered. But only a select few.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The results of the text are for personal gain, so suicide would not work here.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: Offering of all kinds of substances, from precious ones to mundane ones, from sublime ones to disgusting ones, will aid magic effects.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Some rituals are very long, others surprisingly short. The longer ones are the most powerful.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Notes: Some ritual actions are dangerous, many involve consuming taboo, impure, or unhealthy items including intoxicants.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: The text is remarkably non ethical, but it declares the reason for doing these rituals is to steal or usurp another persons wealth and family.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: These are votive, pragmatic rituals performed to address a specific problem.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: Some rituals, especially murder rites, have a large amount of participants, but most are small and include only the sorcerer and maybe an assistant. No evidence of mass or state or larger church versions of these rites.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Notes: For those who are initiates into a lineage or with a teacher who confers the lore, then they are in a father-son relationship with teachers. So literary practitioners have no kinship markings.

Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: I would argue that the written versions of these texts are often for entertainment. The readers would wonder and speculate about such rituals, but it seems that only a few would actually perform them. Contemporary versions seem like pulp texts in the west, cheap and meant to titillate.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: Specific offerings and rites set up a rituals space, but it is temporary, not maintained.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A chiefdom

Notes: These authors and sorcerer practitioners are sometimes elite and sometimes not. Elite Brahmins are found to incorporate non elite practices into the texts by recording them and reframing them in sanskrit context.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Segmentary Lineage

Notes: The text is in sanskrit, so it would be controlled by the top three castes.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Notes: Tantra, especially after the 1700s is considered taboo in Hinduism. These types of tantras on black magic are especially taboo, called tantra-mantra and even the English term black magic is inserted into spoken Indic vernaculars.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Informal education from guru to disciple. Yet, the text also suggests the rituals at hand may be used by a non specialist with few preliminaries.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Mastering the text leads to mastery of the world. Lack of mastery leaves any person open to great dangers from magic or just the horrors of everyday life.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: There are many rituals in the text to manipulate bureaucracy. Little description of performing bureaucracy but many instances of subverting bureaucracy.

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Notes: The source describes rituals to combat armies, to make them ill, to sew dissent. There are not rituals for pure victory, but there are many sub rites to effect the outcome.

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– I don't know

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No